

Accurate Product Recommendation Based On The Image Identified

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ABSTRACT- The project concentrated on developing and providing the customers or users a more simplified and faster purchasing of the products according to their interests. The products when identified by the system on the scan now option provided on the website will generate an accurate product based on the image, that the user may be interested to purchase without searching for the entire products in the store to choose one which he/she may be interested in. The project helps to reduce the time required for customers to search and find a product that he/she may be required or interested. In this method Random Forest Algorithm is used for predicting the exact result for recommendation.

Keywords- *Random Forest Algorithm, Faster R-CNN, Prediction, Recommendation, Image Detection.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning Algorithms helps in providing most of the significant changes in the real world and hence it is also implanting its roots in the ecommerce website that helps the real-life users or customers an immense experience in purchasing as well as searching for their required products in the websites. In this Project, it is concentrated on providing the customers with their required products based on the image uploaded to the website. Here we use the Random Forest method for generating the accurate prediction of the product. The Random Forest Algorithm helps rather than other algorithms that were used because it can accommodate a huge number of classification methods for generating the required result. This may help in generating an accurate result that helps users to identify the exact product that they wish to purchase. Here also uses the Faster R-CNN method for image detection, which is a faster and simplified algorithmic approach for identification and processing of

images. The predicted images will be Recommended to the users as their searched product. The users will also have chances to search for a similar category of products based on the image identified.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Random Forest has become more popular over recent years as a way to predict the result based on a set of items of classifications. So many studies have been conducted in the areas of different factors such as Purchase History, User searches and the Time spent on a product and its characteristics.

Using machine learning techniques of the work presented by Ning Zhang, Yiran Feng and Eung-Joo Lee [1] (2020) tries an improved Faster R-CNN Algorithmic Method to detect the image based on the image uploaded or captured. Faster R-CNN is a combination of RPN and Fast R-CNN that helps generate output of detection categories. On the basics of network architecture Faster R_CNN can be classified as RPN, Detection Network and Basic feature extraction network. The Study helps in generating a report that helps to identify the objects in a much accurate and faster way as it has preferable accuracy over the complicated conditions like illumination influences and complex background to exhibit good detection perfection.

Similar studies have been done in the year 2023 by Pegah Malekpour Alamdari, Nima Jafari Navimipour, Mehdi Hosseinzadeh, Ali Asghar Safaei and Aso Darwesh [2] discuss utilising machine learning methodologies in recommendation of products based on the image captured and analysing the images and its characteristics the image is been identified. The identified image is then passed to the prediction algorithm such as the KNN as it provides less RMSE and MAE values which helps in identifying the

product required by the user based on his purchase history and the value is been recommended to the users that help them to reduce the time spent on the website to search for their required product. In this method Deep learning models are used over the conventional methods for faster identification and detection of the items. The CNN models are compared based on the image used in the ecommerce websites and results are generated based on comparing the CNN methods.

The study conducted by Deepali Vora.[3] (2018) sought a sentimental analysis of product recommendation based on the Random Forest Algorithm. Here Suggests that the ordinal classification has more accuracy on Products. SVM is Popular but Random Forest is effective for robustness to improve sentimental analysis for product recommendation using multiclass classification. Here uses the sentimental analysis review of the product to be inserted into Random Forest Algorithm for generating the result. The Sentimental Analysis Provide a sentiment value for the products based on the reviews or other characteristics and by finding the Random Forest value of the sentimental result will generate an accurate result. The methodologies for language standardization, Pre-processing, Applying Machine learning algorithm Polarity and Recommendation System. The method is most satisfiable as it helps in generating the product for recommendation and gathering the resulting categories based on the result.

III. MOTIVATION

The prediction of an accurate product will help the customers in reducing their overall time for spending time on searching and optimising the required product.

The methodology also helps the disabled persons to purchase products online without the help of others and as accurate results are generated helps them to purchase products much easier and faster. It also simplifies the purchasing of products as the image is captured and helps to identify the products based on the image.

The Recommendation based on the predicted result will enable the suppliers to customize their product categories and help others to identify the least sold products and measures can be taken to raise the product purchase by creating more advertisement and generating a need for the product.

The Methodology helps in overall optimisation of the products.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for generating an accurate product result based on the image based on Random Forest involves the following steps:

- A. **Image Detection:** The first step is to identify a captured image based on Faster R-CNN Algorithm and return the result by processing the image and identify product based on the characteristics.
- B. **Data preparation:** The next step is to prepare the data for the random forest algorithm. This involves selecting a set of features that can help predict the required product. These features can include factors like the user preferred companies, colours user prefer, warranty of the product, Manufacturing year, Search history and so on.
- C. **Train the random forest model:** The next step required is to train the Random Forest Model for generating the required result. The process may include splitting of the dataset and training it based on requirement. The process may also include training the model and evaluating the overall performance of the model. In the process multiple decision trees will be formed and based on the overall decisions made by the trees the result is generated.
- D. **Prediction of product:** Once the model has been trained, we can use it to predict the product based on the user requirements that are specified in the dataset. To do this, we simply input the features of the new item into the model, and the model will output a predicted product. We can also sort the list of items based on the users' requirements and wishes.
- E. **Recommendation of Product:** Once the predicted result is obtained the resulting product is suggested as the recommended product before the users and they can also check for the related result too.

V. BUILD MODEL

The following procedures are used in the project for generating the accurate product that the users wish to purchase.

```

import cv2
import numpy as np
import mysql.connector
from flask import Flask, request, jsonify

app = Flask(__name__)

# connect to the MySQL database
mydb = mysql.connector.connect(
    host="localhost",
    user="root",
    password="",
    database="electroz"
)

@app.route('/upload-image', methods=['POST'])
def upload_image():
    file = request.files['file']
    # Access the file properties
    print(file.filename) # prints the name of the uploaded file
    print(file.content_type) # prints the content type of the file (e.g. image/jpeg)
    # You can read the image file using a library like opencv
    image_to_compare = cv2.imdecode(np.fromstring(file.read(), np.uint8), cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
    
```

Code for identification of product

The prediction is done using the Random Forest Algorithm that may include certain conditions such as the user searching history-based Companies, Colours, Measurements, Warranty Details etc... The resulting product is recommended to users as their result and users may also have a chance to check the product based on the category. The product image has been captured and identified using the Faster R-CNN Algorithm.

The Random Forest method has been used in this project more than that of the other prediction algorithms as it has more classification methodologies. In this project multiple values of the user such as the Companies user prefer, Colours the user prefer, User searched products and so on.

```

from flask import Flask, request
from textblob import TextBlob
app = Flask(__name__)

@app.route('/sentiment', methods=['POST'])
def sentiment_analysis():
    texts = request.json.get('texts')
    sentiment_scores = []
    for text in texts:
        blob = TextBlob(text)
        sentiment = blob.sentiment.polarity
        sentiment_scores.append(sentiment)
    average_sentiment = sum(sentiment_scores) / len(sentiment_scores)
    response = {
        'positive': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s > 0]),
        'negative': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s < 0]),
        'neutral': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s == 0]),
        'average_sentiment': average_sentiment
    }
    return response

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True, port=5000)
    
```

Code for Sentimental value Generation

VI. RESULT

The project Recommends a product based on all the conditions included and provides a result based on all usual characteristics of the user. The result may include a product that will reduce the users time on searching for a product that he wanted online and simplifies all the process.

Image Identification

Product Recommendation

Products of its similar class

VII. CONCLUSION

The project concentrates on generating a result that helps the users to reduce the time spent on purchasing the products based on the Purchase history, User searches and the time spent on viewing the product. But the results generated have gone to further uses such as it helps in optimising the categories for the suppliers and helps the manufacturers to identify the customer standards for purchasing the product. The Project uses Random Forest for prediction of result and also uses Faster R-CNN for identification of the products.

VIII. REFERENCES

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